

Cyberattack and Issues in India : A Study

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Abstract

Data plays a significant part in our everyday lives in the digital era. It is visible in numerous ways. The advent of the digital era has revolutionised our lives, introducing novel methods of communication, organisation, and information retrieval. In addition, it has given rise to a surge in cyber crimes, which are rapidly escalating daily. There is a growing perception that the internet is inherently hazardous. Which necessitates greater examination, oversight, and regulation. Despite the implementation of different safeguards, cyber security remains a significant issue for many individuals. Safeguarding data has emerged as the foremost obstacle in contemporary culture when internet accessibility is widespread. This paper will examine the reasons why this particular approach poses a danger to both the protection of human rights and the security of the digital realm. Ultimately, this will facilitate comprehension of the prevailing methods by which threats in the digital realm are being conceptualised. The potential issues with this framing and strategies for engaging in these discussions. The objective of this study is to determine effective methods of engaging with the government and citizens to safeguard and enhance these rights. Additionally, it emphasises contemporary methodologies and ethical considerations in revolutionising the field of cyber security.

Keywords: digital era, information retrieval, communication, cyber crimes, security, revolutionary methods, etc.

Introduction

The term "Cyber" has its origins in the field of Cybernetics, which is derived from the Greek word "kubernētēs," meaning a pilot or steersman. The user's text is a reference to a source or citation. The individual responsible for popularising it was Norbert Wiener, an American mathematician. In the 1940s, he authored a book titled "Cybernetics." His forecast envisioned a future where a self-governing PC framework, equipped with its feedback loop, would exert dominance and perpetually expand. The term "cyber" did not become associated with digital technology until the 1980s. Cyber refers to anything that is related to or has the

characteristics of information technology, virtual reality, or computers. If we state that we currently reside in a Cyber era, it signifies the era of analysts, virtual reality, and information technology. The cyber cosmos, just like the physical universe, is undergoing expansion. Within the last minute, there have likely been an immense number of updates on popular social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. Our daily routine involves dedicating time to the task of reviewing emails. Approximately 70% of those emails are estimated to be spam, hackers, or dangerous malware attempting to infiltrate your systems and obtain your personal information.

A Cyber Attack is an intentional and malicious attempt by hackers to disrupt or impair the functioning of a computer system or network. Cyberspace refers to the conceptual realm in which communication occurs over computer networks. Originally, the phrase gained popularity in mainstream culture through its association with science fiction. Today, a wide range of individuals, such as technological strategists, industrial executives, security specialists, and the military, utilise it. Cyberspace refers to the global technological environment.

The advancement of technology has led to a heavy dependence on the Internet for fulfilling all of our requirements, which is having an impact on both individuals and society as a whole. It has provided mankind with convenient access to everything while remaining stationary. The Internet enables a wide range of activities, including social networking, online shopping, data storage, gaming, online classes, and job chances. It is employed and ingested in all conceivable manners. The development of the internet has also led to the emergence of cyber-crimes. During the inception of the Internet, the creators were completely unaware of the potential for criminal exploitation. A few years ago, there was a dearth of understanding regarding the potential infractions that may be perpetrated using the internet. As innovation has advanced, so too has the extent of its misuse. Since the beginning of the 21st century, there has been a significant surge in cybercrime.

Cybercrimes pose a potential risk to the security of a nation, the financial well-being of an organisation, and even the personal safety of an individual. India is also witnessing a significant rise in the frequency of digital crimes, keeping pace with other countries.

To ascertain the types of cyber attacks that occur in our country. To gain knowledge of the cyber security techniques that may be employed to prevent the escalation of such destructive

activities. To safeguard one's privacy and personal information and avoid being a victim of cybercrime, it is important to understand the necessary precautions.

Research published by Symantec Corp. (now a division of Broadcom) one year ago revealed that India is the second most targeted country for cyber attacks globally, following the United States and China. This was widely publicised in the media. The Indian legal framework, particularly the Indian IT Act 2000, does not provide comprehensive protection to its citizens against emerging methods of attack such as phishing, SIM jacking, ransomware, mobile payment fraud, bank fraud, malware attacks, social engineering, and DDoS attacks, which are becoming common in today's world. (2)

In his work, Das (2013) examines the various ways in which the Internet has demonstrated its efficiency. It is crucial to ensure that the Internet does not become a breeding ground for illicit activities and a platform for promoting malicious actions. According to him, while the government will play a significant role, the primary responsibility for preventing fraud lies with commercial companies that should develop software with the capability to detect and prevent fraudulent activities. (3)

Cyber Crimes

Cybercrime can be defined as any criminal activity or wrongdoing that involves electronic communications or information systems, including devices, the internet, or a combination of these elements.

Cybercrime is a criminal activity that involves the utilisation of a structured system and a network. The computer could have been employed in the perpetration of the crime, or it could be the subject or focus. Digital crimes refer to intentional offences committed against individuals, resulting in harm to their reputation or causing direct or indirect physical or psychological damage, using modern technology. For instance, web chat rooms, cell phones, messages or emails, and notification feeds. These criminal activities present a significant risk to the nation's security and economic well-being. Crimes of this nature, particularly those involving hacking, copyright infringement, and child pornography, attract significant attention and scrutiny. Security concerns are heightened when confidential information is either prohibited or exposed, whether through legal means or otherwise. The exponential expansion

of electronic commerce (e-commerce) and online share trading has resulted in a remarkable increase in occurrences of cybercrimes.

Cyber crimes can be primarily categorised into three major classifications:

1. Personal cybercrimes
2. Cybercrimes targeting property
3. Cybercrimes targeting government

Cyber Crimes against People

Cybercrimes targeting individuals encompass a range of offences, including the dissemination of Child pornography and the intimidation of individuals through the use of personal computers, such as email. The dissemination, circulation, publishing, and distribution of explicit material, including pornography and public nudity, is considered a significant form of cybercrime in contemporary society. The impact of such atrocities on humanity is negligible. Cybercrime poses a significant threat to the development of the younger generation, as it inflicts permanent damage and harm if left unchecked.

Cyber harassment constitutes an independent form of cybercrime. Diverse manifestations of harassment can and can transpire in the realm of the internet or via its utilisation. Harassment can manifest in several forms, including but not limited to sexual, racial, religious, or other types. Individuals who engage in such harassment are likewise engaging in acts of cybercrime. Cyberbullying can potentially lead to criminal activities that infringe upon the privacy of individuals.

Engaging in the infringement of Internet citizens' privacy constitutes a grave offence. No one appreciates being subjected to assault by another individual on the sacred and deeply significant aspect of their privacy, which is bestowed upon citizens through the Internet.

Cyber Crimes against Property

The second categorization of cyber attacks pertains to cybercrimes against various forms of property. Computer crime includes acts such as PC vandalism (the intentional

destruction of others' property), the dissemination of harmful programs, the embezzlement of funds from financial institutions, and the theft of secret data and information.

A start-up organisation situated in Mumbai incurred significant financial losses in their business after a large industry competitor illicitly obtained the technical database from their computers with the aid of a corporate cyber espionage agent.

Cyber Crimes Targeting Government

The proliferation of the internet has revealed that individuals and organisations are employing the cyberspace infrastructure to intimidate foreign governments and also to intimidate the citizens of a country. Terrorism occurs when an individual deliberately disrupts or damages an administration, state, or military-operated website.

Cyber-crime in India

The 2019 Internet Crime Report, published by the United States Internet Crime Complaint Centre (IC3) of the Federal Bureau of Investigation, reveals that India ranks third globally among the top 20 nations affected by cybercrimes. The research states that, apart from the USA, the United Kingdom had the highest number of cybercrime victims, with a total of 93,796. Canada followed with 3,721 victims, and India had 2,901.

According to the latest data from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), there were a total of 27,248 reported cases of cyber-attacks in India in 2018. 1,205 instances of cyber-attacks were reported in Telangana simultaneously. The National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal, initiated by the Central government one year ago, has received 33,152 complaints to date, resulting in the filing of 790 First Information Reports (FIRs). The user's text is "[5]".

Cybercrime falls within the scope of the IT Act, but it is not limited to it. Certain provisions also fall within the purview of the Indian Penal Code.

Following are a few examples of Cybercrime in India:

1. **E-Mail Bomb:** An instance of Internet abuse in which a substantial volume of emails is deliberately sent to a specific email address to overwhelm the mailbox, incapacitating the mail server supporting the address, and causing the service to fail.

2. Hacking: Hacking refers to the deliberate misuse of a computer system or a private network within a computer. In essence, it refers to the unauthorised manipulation or control of computer security systems for illicit purposes. It is accomplished by proficient hackers who possess advanced abilities in circumventing a security system.
3. Propagating computer malware: A computer infection refers to a harmful program intentionally installed on a user's computer without their knowledge, to cause harm, such as data destruction, and carrying out destructive actions. The virus can propagate via email, USB drives, multimedia files, and the internet.
4. Phishing refers to cybercrime in which individuals are contacted over email, phone, or instant messaging by someone pretending to be a legitimate organisation to deceive them into providing sensitive information such as personal data, financial details, credit card information, and passwords. The data is subsequently utilised to access important records and has the potential to result in substantial fraud, identity theft, and financial detriment.
5. Identity theft: Identity theft refers to the act of acquiring an individual's confidential or financial information with the sole intention of conducting transactions or making purchases using that person's name or identity. It involves gaining unauthorised entry to corporate databases to pilfer lists of client information and eradicating their confidential and financial data. The offender will be sentenced to imprisonment, which might extend up to three years, and may also be liable to pay a fine of up to one lakh rupees.

Cyber Security

A hospital experiences a data breach, the electricity system is compromised, and derogatory comments about a political leader are shared on a social media platform. Although these scenarios may appear distinct, they can all be categorised as instances of cyber security. Cyber security is typically presented by the government and corporations.

Cybersecurity refers to the methods and strategies implemented to safeguard data. This applies to digital data. Data that is stored, transported, or being used on an information network, server, or system. Data is the vital essence of the digital realm. Data, ranging from personal information to important governmental communications, is transmitted through networks in large volumes and stored on various devices and data centres. Cybersecurity and

technology are inseparable topics. The IT Act of 2000 defines "cyber-security" as the safeguarding of devices and the information held inside them against unauthorised access, use, disclosure, disruption, alteration, or destruction.

Government institutions and regulation for cyber security:

- 1) The National Technical Research Organisation (NTRO) is the primary organisation responsible for safeguarding the nation's vital infrastructure and managing all cyber security incidents in critical sectors of the country.
- 2) The Indian Computer Emergency Response Team is responsible for conducting investigations, making predictions, and issuing alerts regarding cyber security threats and breaches.

Techniques of Cyber Security

1. Enhanced Password Security: Employing a robust and intricate password is a simple measure to enhance the security of your system. For example, a password that includes special characters, numbers, and letters. Frequently updating it can effectively prevent brute-force password cracking.

2. Verification of knowledge: Consistently staying informed and Exercising careful discretion: Programmers, often known as hackers, can exploit email and web platforms in various ways. It is important to exercise caution when using these platforms. Implementing system updates and regularly performing backups is an effective approach to ensure the accessibility of your data and to safeguard against and rectify any system glitches or flaws.

3. Malware scanners are software programs that detect and analyse dangerous code, as well as destructive viruses, in all files stored on a computer. Viruses, worms, and Trojan horses are categorised as malware, which refers to malicious software.

4. Firewalls are software programs or hardware components that effectively filter out hackers, viruses, and worms that try to access your device via the internet. Every incoming or outgoing message on the web is subjected to the firewall, which scrutinises each message and prevents those that violate necessary safety protocols.

Installing anti-virus software is an essential measure to safeguard your PC network against infections. It thoroughly checks your emails and system documents for viruses that enter your

operating system. An effective antivirus software incorporates regular updates and should be compatible with the system.

A Case Study

Legal case about taxation in the state of Andhra Pradesh

The proprietor of a plastic manufacturing enterprise in Andhra Pradesh was apprehended by authorities. The Vigilance Department discovered a sum of Twenty-Two Crore in cash at his residence. The individuals sought specific information and a rationale from the individual concerning the undisclosed funds. The defendant submitted 6,000 coupons as evidence to verify the legitimacy of the enterprise. However, upon thorough scrutiny of the vouchers and data stored in his personal computers, it was discovered that all the vouchers had been created after the raids. It was discovered that five enterprises were operating under the umbrella of a single corporation, and it is alleged that they used counterfeit and computer-generated vouchers to fabricate sales records and evade taxes. Consequently, the interrogation techniques employed by the top executive of Andhra Pradesh became evident when the department personnel seized the computers utilised by the suspect.

The Bank NSP Case

The case of Bank NSP involves a Bank Management Trainee who was employed and was in the process of getting married. The couple communicated often through email and SMS, utilising the company's computer. Eventually, the two individuals separated and the young woman proceeded to construct fraudulent email accounts under the guise of "Indian Bar Associations". She then proceeded to send emails to the man's international clients. She utilised the personal computer provided by the bank to do this task. The man's company experienced a significant decline in its customer base and subsequently filed a lawsuit against the bank to seek compensation for the resulting financial loss. The bank was deemed accountable and legally responsible for the transmission of emails conducted through the bank's system or personal computer.

The case of Tamil Nadu v. Suhas Katti

This case is associated with the dissemination of graphic, slanderous, and distressing messages about a divorced woman in the Yahoo messaging group. The claimed perpetrator sent

additional e-mails to the victim as evidence, using a false e-mail account created in the victim's name. The act of posting the message led to bothersome phone calls being made to the woman since it was believed that she was engaging in solicitation. In response to a complaint lodged by the victim in February 2004, the Police successfully located and apprehended the accused in Mumbai within a few days. The defendant was a familiar acquaintance of the victim and allegedly expressed interest in marrying her. Nevertheless, she wedded someone else. Subsequently, the marriage ended in divorce, prompting the accused to resume communication with her. The accused resorted to online abuse in response to her unwillingness to marry him. During the prosecution, a total of 12 witnesses were interviewed and all relevant papers were officially marked as Exhibits. The court relied on expert witnesses and other evidence presented, including testimony from the owners of the Cyber Cafe. Based on this, the court reached a definitive conclusion that the crime had been proven and proceeded to convict the accused. This marks the first instance in Tamil Nadu where the perpetrator has been found guilty under section 67 of the IT Act in India.

Internet-based fraudulent activity involving credit cards on the e-Bay platform [9]

The Rourkela police have dismantled a criminal network involved in an internet fraud of Rs. 12.5 lakh. The accused's modus operandi involved hacking into the eBay India site and making purchases using the names of credit cardholders. Two men, including the alleged mastermind Debasis Pandit, who is a BCA student, were apprehended and taken to the court of the sub-divisional judicial magistrate in Rourkela. Rabi Narayan Sahu is the other man who has been captured. A legal case has been filed against the accused individual under Sections 420 and 34 of the Indian Penal Code, as well as Section 66 of the IT Act.

Debasis Pandit allegedly breached the security of the eBay India website and obtained the personal information of approximately 700 individuals who have credit cards. Subsequently, he proceeded to make purchases by utilising their passwords. The eBay authorities became aware of the fraud when they discovered that purchases were made from Rourkela, although the clients were located in locations like Bangalore, Baroda, Jaipur, and even London. After receiving complaints from certain clients, the corporation reported the situation to the Rourkela police.

Cyber Ethics and Methods to Prevent Cyber Attack

Internet etiquette, commonly known as netiquette, pertains to the set of principles governing appropriate behaviour on the Internet. The cardinal principle is to refrain from engaging in any activities in the cyber realm that one would deem unethical or unlawful.

1. Utilise the internet to communicate and engage with others. Email and messaging facilitate the maintenance of connections with family, friends, and colleagues. Disseminating novel ideas, ideas, and knowledge to those residing in the same city or across the globe.

2. Avoid disclosing or transmitting your personal information, such as bank account number, password, ATM PIN, and similar details, over an unsecured network, including unencrypted email. Websites lacking a lock icon and the "https" prefix in the browser's address bar are considered unencrypted sites. The letter "s" in this context represents the word "secure" and serves as an indication that the website is both secure and safe.

3. Refrain from registering on any social networking platforms or websites unless they are verified and genuine.

4. It is imperative to consistently refresh and upgrade the operating framework. It is advisable to install and regularly update software such as firewalls, antivirus, and antispyware programs on personal computers.

5. Avoid accessing, tracking, and engaging with spam and untrustworthy websites or links.

6. Refrain from engaging in online harassment or bullying. Avoid the use of abusive language or statements. Refrain from engaging in name-calling, defaming individuals, sharing embarrassing or graphic images of them, or intentionally causing harm to them.

The internet is often regarded as the largest repository of information, covering a vast array of subjects across all fields of expertise. Therefore, it is imperative to utilise this data in a manner that is both ethical and compliant with the law.

8. Refrain from divulging your password to anyone and abstain from accessing others' accounts using their passwords.

9. Avoid disclosing your personal information to anyone, as there is a significant likelihood of it being misused by others, resulting in negative repercussions for you.

10. Avoid clicking on pop-ups that present site surveys or studies on e-commerce websites or any other sites, as they may contain harmful software. When we acknowledge or follow pop-ups, a download is initiated in the background, and the downloaded file contains malware and malicious code. This type of download is commonly referred to as a drive-by-download.

11. Always adhere to copyrighted data and only download games or recordings if they are permissible.

12. Do not engage in the act of intentionally transmitting any form of malicious software to other individuals' computers to cause corruption.

13. It is important to refrain from assuming false identities or creating fraudulent accounts impersonating others, as this behaviour can lead to legal consequences for both yourself and the person being impersonated.

These are a few cyber ethics that one must adhere to when using the internet. We adhere to suitable ideals and behaviours in our lives from an early age, just as we do in the realm of cyberspace.

Conclusion

India, a nation with a population of 1.3 billion, has the most affordable data costs globally. Ensuring the security of data and information is increasingly crucial as networks continue to advance. This study demonstrates that as cyberspace and technology continue to advance, the prevalence of cyber risks will also escalate. To safeguard data, it is imperative to employ Cybersecurity methods such as implementing firewalls, maintaining robust passwords, installing antivirus software, and practising proactive efforts to avoid cyber-attacks. India's passive strategy of safeguarding its cyber infrastructure only in response to cyber security incidents needs to be transformed into a proactive approach. It is currently necessary. To defend the rule of law, it is necessary to have awareness, firm modifications, criminal provisions, and a cyber security policy to protect rights and privacy.

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